

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12789114>

DIGITALIZATION IN ECONOMY

Akrom Omonov

Professor of Banking department of
Tashkent Institute of Finance

Sabirova Nodira Komil qizi

Republic of Uzbekistan BANKING-FINANCE ACADEMY, MSc

Abstract: *Every aspect of the economy is being impacted by the widespread digitalization. Because digitization is so widespread, it is challenging to identify and measure its economic effects. The term "digital sector" or a group of "digital establishments" whose development and evolution may be likened to those of traditional industries like manufacturing and agriculture is not defined by standard categories. Even if it is challenging and sometimes subjective to quantify digitalization, it is nonetheless useful to attempt to categorize this activity in order to better understand how it has changed in relation to total economic activity. Gaining a deeper comprehension of the impact of digitalization on the economy can help with the analysis of future growth, inflation dynamics, labor market development, technical advancements, and shock transmission.*

Key words: *digital economy, digital technology, group seven countries (Canada, France, Germany, Italy, the UK and USA as well as European Union), ICT (information and technologies), OECD(the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development), fourth industrial revolution, research and development (R&D),*

Annotatsiya: *Raqamlashtirish keng tarqalib, iqtisodiyotning barcha tarmoqlariga ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda. Raqamlashtirishning keng tarqalgan tabiati uning iqtisodiy ta'sirini ajratish va miqdoriy baholashni qiyinlashtiradi. Standart tasniflar o'sishi va evolyutsiyasi ishlab chiqarish va qishloq xo'jaligi kabi boshqa tarmoqlar bilan taqqoslanishi mumkin bo'lgan "raqamli sektor" yoki "raqamli muassasalar" to'plamini aniqlamaydi. Raqamlashtirishni miqdoriy baholash vazifasi qiyin va biroz sub'ektiv bo'lsa-da, uning umumiy iqtisodiy faoliyatga nisbatan evolyutsiyasini*

yaxshiroq tushunish uchun ushbu faoliyat atrofida bir quti qo'yishga urinish hali ham foydalidir. Raqamlashtirishning iqtisodiyotga ta'sirini yaxshiroq tushunish mehnat bozorlari evolyutsiyasini, inflyatsiya dinamikasini, texnologik taraqqiyotni, kelajakdagi o'sishni va zarbalarning uzatilishini tahlil qilishga yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli iqtisodiyot, raqamli texnologiyalar, ettinchi guruh mamlakatlari (Kanada, Frantsiya, Germaniya, Italiya, Buyuk Britaniya va AQSh hamda Yevropa Ittifoqi), AKT (axborot va texnologiyalar), OECD (Iqtisodiy hamkorlik va taraqqiyot tashkiloti), to'rtinchi sanoat inqilobi, tadqiqot va ishlanmalar (R&D).

Аннотация: *Цифровизация носит всеобъемлющий характер и затрагивает все отрасли экономики. Повсеместный характер цифровизации затрудняет выделение и количественную оценку ее экономического воздействия. Стандартные классификации не определяют «цифровой сектор» или набор «цифровых предприятий», рост и эволюцию которых можно сравнить с другими секторами, такими как производство и сельское хозяйство. Хотя задача количественной оценки цифровизации сложна и несколько субъективна, все же имеет смысл попытаться ограничить эту деятельность, чтобы лучше понять ее эволюцию относительно общей экономической активности. Лучшее понимание влияния цифровизации на экономику поможет проанализировать эволюцию рынков труда, динамику инфляции, технологический прогресс, будущий рост и передачу шоков.*

Ключевые слова: *цифровая экономика, цифровые технологии, семь стран группы (Канада, Франция, Германия, Италия, Великобритания и США, а также Европейский Союз), ИКТ (информация и технологии), OECD (Организация экономического сотрудничества и развития), четвертая промышленная революция, исследования и разработки (R&D).*

Because of its reliance on internet access, the digital economy was once known as the web economy, the internet economy, or the new economy. Economists and corporate executives contend, however, that the digital economy is more sophisticated and intricate than the internet economy. It may be defined as simply the financial benefit obtained from the internet. The transition from the third to the fourth industrial revolutions is reflected in the digital economy. The shift from analog electrical and mechanical devices to digital technology in the late 20th century is referred to as the third industrial revolution, or occasionally the "digital revolution." Since modern technologies continue to connect the real and virtual worlds, the fourth industrial revolution builds upon the success of the digital revolution.

A nation's ability to expand economically depends on its economy's level of digitalization, which also has a big impact on productivity and makes technological innovation impossible to achieve without it. The Group seven countries' remarkable accomplishment of rapid economic development may be attributed to a number of causes, including increased levels of technical innovation. The commercial landscape of the Group seven countries has evolved in recent years due to the digitization of economies brought about by advances in information and communication technologies (ICTs). These countries' economy has benefited from these advances in digitization in terms of higher productivity, social transformation, and industrial development. 58% of the world's net worth is accounted for by these seven nations (OECD, 2019). Furthermore, these countries' economic performance has improved dramatically over time. Additionally, the big seven economies have improved their economic and innovative performance by investing billions of dollars in research and development (R&D). Therefore, it is essential to examine how R&D and digitalization affect technical innovation as it relates to the Group 7 nations. Because of this, the Group 7 nations hold a sizable portion of the global net worth, have advanced digitalization, and have seen a rise in technical innovation. There is a wealth of research on the factors that influence technological innovation. A number of factors are seen to be significant drivers of technological innovation, including income, imports, human capital, institutional quality, financial development, debt financing, corruption, knowledge spillovers, and—above all—investments in research and development.

The internet's introduction in the 1990s, which changed the industrial and economic structures, is largely responsible for the economy's current digitalization (Schwab, 2017). The economy has become more digital throughout time, especially since the fourth industrial revolution began. Artificial intelligence and the automation of the economy are terms used to describe how digital technologies have changed the way businesses operate and how they are structured (Su et al., 2020). According to Pradhan et al. (2019), the term "digitalization" in the economy refers to the advancement of digital technologies that boost social production efficiency. Ideas, information, creativity, and innovation are the cornerstones of the digital economy (Johnson, 2019). The process of digitization is changing economies all around the world. But the pace of advancement in digital technology is slow, and it takes time for it to reach consumers (Galichkina, 2014). Furthermore, there is a notable coordination gap across nations when it comes to the advancement of digital technology. Modern enterprises and organizations have benefited greatly from technical advancements, which have multiplied the global production. The development of digital formats, the internet of things, and information and communication technologies (ICTs) has altered

the nature of business. Furthermore, as a result of these developments, organizational structure and institutional quality have significantly altered. National economies have benefited from the economy's progress toward digitization in terms of increased productivity, social transformation, and industrial growth. For these reasons, the new industrial revolution is sometimes referred to as the phenomena of digitization in the economy (Lee et al., 2018).

Due to the considerable financial risk associated with businesses, banks are frequently hesitant to finance creative ideas, despite the fact that innovation comes at a large cost for which bank financing is necessary. Therefore, it is believed that a high level of financial risk prevents technical progress. In conclusion, the economy's digitization and R&D spending have a significant impact on technological innovation. However, reducing financial risk is necessary to enjoy the advantages of these elements. Therefore, it is essential to examine the connections between the economy's digitization, research and development spending, and financial risk associated with technological innovation.

Four factors are used to examine the digital economy (Semjachkov, 2017): the value factor, technology, penetration rate, and employment sector. Physical labor is seen to be replaced by its mental form when there is a simultaneous decrease in the percentage of workers employed in the production sector and a rise in the percentage of workers engaged in the services sector. These kinds of statistics, as they exist, are not indicative of the degree of development of the digital sector, given the explosive increase in the number of trade workers, attorneys, and other professionals who fit into the category of mental labor. Data networks that link various locations are referred to as penetration rates, and as such, they may have an effect on the construction of the global economic space. Data networks are a feature unique to contemporary civilization. The shift to a digital economy is reflected in the volume of data and the speed at which it is transferred. The value component is a prerequisite for the expansion of the data production, transit, processing, and storage's economic value. A shift is presumed if this developing trend is more pronounced in the economic sphere than in production and agriculture. Furthermore, in these circumstances, data becomes a subject of commercial exchanges. In addition to their reputation as the engines of economic progress, the appearance of new technologies is the first sign of a shift in the economic systems.

Research indicates that the proportion of ICTs and ICT-enabled services in emerging and developing nations is increasing. To put it another way, these nations have been able to boost their GDP by providing ICTs and services enabled by ICTs to other nations. ICT-enabled services are defined by the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) as digital services that are provided remotely. According to the USA's 2014 economic research, 48% of ICT and ICT-enabled services were imported and 54% were exported. In terms of ICT and ICT-enabled services, the emerging and developing economies, headed by China and India,

accounted for 27% of imports and 33% of exports (IMF February 2018 Measuring the Digital Economy (Washington D.C.: International Monetary Fund).

In conclusion, the lives of regular people and enterprises are being overtaken by digital technology. The digital industry is a whole in and of itself, not only a support system for other industrial sectors. It is anticipated that the ICT and ICT-enabled services industry will continue to expand as digitalization increases. Investing in and marketing digital goods and services domestically will inevitably boost a nation's economy, both directly through ICT use and indirectly through ICT support for other businesses.

LITERATURE

Galichkina (2014) (PDF) *digitalization in economy and innovation: The effect on social and economic processes*. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/335015720_Digitalization_in_Economy_and_Innovation_The_Effect_on_Social_and_Economic_Processes (Accessed: 14 April 2024).

Lee (2018) *A study on the factors affecting decrease in the government corruption and mediating effects of the development of ICT and E-GOVERNMENT-A cross-country analysis*, *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*. Available at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2199853122002967> (Accessed: 14 April 2024).

Pradhan, R.P. et al. (2018) *Short-term and long-term dynamics of venture capital and economic growth in a Digital Economy: A Study of European countries, Technology in Society*. Available at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0160791X18301829> (Accessed: 14 April 2024).

Schwab (2017) *The Fourth Industrial Revolution*. Available at: https://law.unimelb.edu.au/_data/assets/pdf_file/0005/3385454/Schwab-The_Fourth_Industrial_Revolution_Klaus_S.pdf (Accessed: 14 April 2024).

Semjachkov, С.К. (2019) *ЦИФРОВАЯ ЭКОНОМИКА И ЕЕ РОЛЬ В УПРАВЛЕНИИ СОВРЕМЕННЫМИ СОЦИАЛЬНО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИМИ ОТНОШЕНИЯМИ*, *КиберЛенинка*. Available at: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/tsifrovaya-ekonomika-i-ee-rol-v-upravlenii-sovremennymi-sotsialno-ekonomicheskimi-otnosheniyami-1> (Accessed: 14 April 2024).

Su et al (2020) *Financial implications of fourth industrial revolution: Can bitcoin improve prospects of energy investment?*, *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*. Available at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0040162520310040> (Accessed: 14 April 2024).